

Computation of Binomial Coefficient with Real Number

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Abstract: This paper presents a technique to compute the binomial coefficients with real numbers. This technique is used as application in computing and mathematical sciences.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-12], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series [11-20] was developed with new idea of binomial coefficients.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series is derived from the multiple summations of a geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial geometric series [17-33] refers to the binomial coefficient [29-40].

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \text{ and } V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r)}{r!},$$

where r is a positive integer and n is non-negative integer. Note that $V_n^0 = V_0^0 = 0! = 1$.

3. Binomial Coefficient with Real Number

The binomial coefficient with real number is introduced as follows:

$$V_x^n = \frac{(x+1)(x+2)(x+3) \cdots (x+n)}{n!},$$

where n is a positive integer, x is a non-negative real number, and V_x^n is a binomial coefficient. Note that $V_x^0 = V_0^0 = 0! = 1$.

Examples for the binomial coefficient with real number are given below:

$$V_{0.072}^5 = \frac{(0.072+1)(0.072+2)(0.072+3)(0.072+4)(0.072+5)}{5!}.$$

$$R_{1.5}^1 = \frac{(1+1.5)}{0!} = 2.5.$$

$$V_{3/10}^4 = \frac{\left(\frac{3}{10}+1\right)\left(\frac{3}{10}+2\right)\left(\frac{3}{10}+3\right)\left(\frac{3}{10}+4\right)}{4!}.$$

$$V_0^7 = \frac{(0+1)(0+2)(0+3)(0+4)(0+5)(0+6)(0+7)}{7!} = 1.$$

Similarly, we can constitute other binomial coefficients with real numbers.

4. Conclusion

In this article, a technique has been introduced to computer a binomial coefficient with real number. This technique is used as application in computing and mathematical sciences.

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